

1 **Water quality in the Tropical Andes Hotspot: the**
2 **Yacuambi river (southeastern Ecuador)**

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12 **HIGHLIGHTS:**

- 13 • Yacuambi river waters were good and medium according to Water Quality Index.
14 • Water is inadequate for drinking, preservation of aquatic life and irrigation.
15 • Color, As and fecal coliforms exceeded human consumption limits in all samples.
16 • All samples exceeded the threshold of preservation for aquatic life for Pb.
17 • Yacuambi river waters are unsuitable for irrigation due to As and fecal coliforms.

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27 **Abstract**

28 Yacuambi river waters (southeast Ecuador, Amazonian region) were assessed to evaluate
29 the potential risk to populations, who use it for drinking and irrigation, and ecosystems,
30 which are part of Tropical Andes hotspot and considered some of the most biodiverse in
31 the world. The water quality index was calculated and some quality parameters were
32 checked to comply with Ecuadorian and North American standards for human
33 consumption, preservation of aquatic life and irrigation.

34 Four samplings were carried out in six stations covering the entire length of the Yacuambi
35 river. Several parameters were analyzed: pH, conductivity, dissolved oxygen, temperature,
36 color, phosphates, nitrite, nitrate, biochemical oxygen demand, chemical oxygen demand,
37 total solids, turbidity, metals (Ba, Cd, Cr, Pb, As and Hg), pesticides and fecal coliforms.

38 The water quality in the Yacuambi river was good and medium according to the
39 classification of the Water Quality Index. However, it was unsuitable for human
40 consumption, preservation of aquatic life and irrigation according to Ecuadorian and North
41 American standards. Arsenic, color and fecal coliforms exceeded the limits for human
42 consumption in all samples tested. Thresholds of preservation of aquatic life were
43 exceeded in all samples in the case of Pb and in some samples for As, pH, nitrite and
44 nitrate. Arsenic and fecal coliforms made Yacuambi river waters unsuitable for irrigation.

45

46 **Keywords**

47 Pollution; Metals; Trace elements; Pesticides; Zamora-Chinchiipe; Environmental
48 protection.

49

50 **1 Introduction**

51 Industrialization and economic growth in developing countries have led to an interest in
52 pollution of aquatic ecosystems (Diop et al., 2015; Duong et al., 2014; Mwanamoki et al.,
53 2014). Ecuador has made remarkable progress in recent years. However, a significant
54 percentage of the population lives below the poverty line and lack access to safely
55 managed drinking water (WHO/UNICEF, 2015). This problem is intensified in the
56 Ecuadorian Andes, well known for its mining activities (Adler Miserendino et al., 2013;
57 Velásquez-López et al., 2011, 2010; Zarroca et al., 2015).

58 Gold placer mining is the simplest way to extract gold (López-Blanco et al., 2015). This
59 method consists in extracting the sediment located in the river bed and in the floodplain,
60 until reaching the bedrock, at most 10 m deep (Stubblefield et al., 2005). Sediment
61 extraction is usually carried out with pumps or excavators. The extracted material contains
62 high purity gold nuggets, which are separated from the sediment around the river. The
63 material is sieved using water from the river and introduced into small channels that have a
64 textile in the bottom. The gold particles are denser, fall to the bottom and are retained in
65 this material. All the sediment from the river bed and the floodplain are deposited back into
66 the river (Byambaa and Todo, 2011).

67 When gold particles obtained are too small, amalgamation with Hg is used. In this process,
68 a solution of Hg is added to these particles to form an Au-Hg amalgam, which is burnt with
69 a blowtorch and bigger pure gold nuggets are produced (López-Blanco et al., 2015). In
70 many cases, amalgamation is carried out on the river banks and releases Hg either
71 dissolved in water or emitted into the atmosphere. Hg pollutes the environment, can be
72 biomagnified through the food chain and can cause toxicity to humans and living beings
73 (Kapia et al., 2016; Krupskaya et al., 2013). Artisanal scale mining releases 1,400
74 tonnes/year of Hg to land, water, and air (United Nations Environment Programme,

75 2013a). Approximately half of it (727 tonnes/year) is emitted to the air, making artisanal
76 scale mining the largest source of anthropogenic Hg emissions (United Nations
77 Environment Programme, 2013b).

78 Gold placer mining can also provoke other environmental problems (Batsaikhan et al.,
79 2016). The turbidity of water may increase, because the bottom sediment is resuspended.
80 The deep sediment could be moved to the top, suffering a change in redox potential from
81 anaerobic to aerobic conditions, releasing part of the heavy metals contained therein, such
82 as Zn, Cu, Cd, Mn, Pb, Ni, Fe, Cr, As, Hg and Se (Chakraborty et al., 2016). The
83 movement of sediments can significantly alter the relief and landscape. In some cases,
84 rivers have been diverted to facilitate sediment extraction and have disappeared.

85 Efforts to reduce the negative impacts of gold placer mining are taking place in Papua New
86 Guinea (Kapia et al., 2016), China (Egidarev and Simonov, 2015), Malaysia (Eam et al.,
87 2013), the Bering Sea (Jewett and Naidu, 2000), Russia (Krupskaya et al., 2014, 2013;
88 Litvintsev, 2015; Panfilov et al., 2014) and South Africa (Tucker et al., 2016).

89 The Yacuambi river, located in the southeast of Ecuador, is exposed to the threats of gold
90 placer mining in the area and other activities that could endanger the quality of its waters
91 (López-Blanco et al., 2015). Agriculture uses pesticides that could end up in the river. In
92 addition, agricultural fertilizers and manure from livestock could increase the content of
93 organic matter and coliforms in the water. The nearby towns discharge sewage into the
94 Yacuambi river without prior treatment. Much urban waste is deposited in the banks of the
95 river due to the lack of municipal solid waste management systems (Gallardo et al., 2013).

96 The Yacuambi river is the main water source to populations within its catchment. Many of
97 the inhabitants of the Yacuambi basin drink water directly from the river without any
98 previous purification. It is also used for irrigation and fishes serve as a food source to local
99 communities (Gallardo et al., 2013). Furthermore, Yacuambi catchment is located within

100 the Northwestern Andean montane forests, considered one of the most biodiverse areas in
101 the world by the WWF's Global 200 (Olson and Dinerstein, 2002) and the list of hotspots
102 proposed by Myers et al. (2000). It is also a tributary of the Amazon river. Despite the risk
103 for communities and the ecosystem, there are few previous studies on the quality of
104 Yacuambi river.

105 This study aims to evaluate the risk of the Yacuambi river for populations who use it for
106 drinking and irrigation and for the ecosystem, considered one of the most biodiverse in the
107 world. For this purpose, the water quality index designed by Brown et al. (1970) was used.
108 Moreover, compliance to Ecuadorian and North American standards for human
109 consumption, preservation of aquatic life and irrigation was checked.

110 **2 Materials and methods**

111 **2.1 Study area: Yacuambi river**

112 The Yacuambi river (Figure 1) is located in the southeast of Ecuador, in the Yacuambi
113 canton, Zamora-Chinchipe province, Amazonian region. It rises in the northern area of the
114 canton, in the Andes mountains and runs from north to south along the 50 km long
115 Yacuambi valley. It has many tributaries on both banks, among which are the rivers
116 Tutupali, Yacuchingari, Shingata, Corral Huaycu, Garcelán, Negro and Quimi. Upon
117 reaching the town of La Saquea, it flows into the river Zamora, part of the upper Amazon
118 river basin.

119 Yacuambi river basin lies between longitudes $78^{\circ} 05'$ and $78^{\circ} 43'$ W and between latitudes
120 $03^{\circ} 31'$ and $03^{\circ} 50'$ S. The area of the Yacuambi river basin is 126,580 ha, with a perimeter
121 of 169.55 km. It is an elongated basin with a form factor of 0.241. The average height of
122 the basin is 2,200 masl. The average slope is around 30% and, therefore, the relief is steep
123 (Fundación Ecológica Arcoiris, 2007).

124 There are many settlements on the banks of Yacuambi river, among which are Tutupali, 28
125 de Mayo and La Paz. There is a relevant presence of indigenous communities, mainly
126 Saraguros and Shuars. The Yacuambi canton is the main settlement of the ethnic group
127 Saraguro in Zamora Chinchipe province. The populations' main source of water are nearby
128 rivers and in many cases the water is not treated for consumption.

129 In the Yacuambi river basin, human activities threaten the quality of its waters, such as
130 mining, agriculture, cattle raising and sewage discharges. In the Yacuambi canton, metal
131 mining concessions account for 43,146 ha, i.e. 34% of the 126,000 ha estimated area with
132 exploitable mineral resources. Both banks of the Yacuambi river have concessions to
133 mining activities (Fundación Ecológica Arcoiris, 2007).

134 Agriculture and livestock occupy a significant area of the Yacuambi canton. These
135 activities could lead to pesticide contamination and increased organic matter in the water
136 by the use of fertilizers and animal manure spills. The main crops grown in the area are:
137 cane, cassava, coffee, cocoa, annatto, bananas, baby bananas, yams, and citrus. Livestock
138 typically consists of cows and, to a lesser extent pigs, horses and chickens. Cows occupy a
139 significant part of the banks of the river, where they go to drink (Fundación Ecológica
140 Arcoiris, 2007).

141 The nearby towns discharge into the Yacuambi river a large amount of raw sewage. In
142 addition, many urban wastes are deposited in the banks of the river due to the lack of
143 municipal solid waste management systems.

144 The area has a high ecological value. Around 60% of the Yacuambi basin is occupied by
145 native forest and 57,000 ha of Yacuambi canton (44% of the total area) is a nature reserve
146 called Yacuambi. Furthermore, the lagoons of el Condorcillo, a proposed Ramsar area, are
147 located inside the nature reserve Yacuambi. Some endangered species have been recorded
148 around these lagoons. This is the case for two mammals, the spectacled bear (*Tremarctos*

149 *ornatus*) and the mountain tapir (*Tapirus pinchaque*), and a reptile, the Parker's
 150 Pholidobolus (*Macropholidus annectens*).

151 Considering a larger scale, Yacuambi basin is part of the Northwestern Andean montane
 152 forests, cataloged within the WWF's Global 200 project as an area of exceptional
 153 biodiversity and representative of its ecosystems (Olson and Dinerstein, 2002).

154 These forests are also part of the Tropical Andes Hotspot. A hotspot is one of the 25 most
 155 biodiverse areas globally, i.e. it comprises at least 0.5% or 1,500 species of vascular plants
 156 as endemics, and has lost at least 70% of its primary vegetation (Myers et al., 2000). The
 157 25 hotspots include 133,149 plant species (44% of all plant species in the world) and 9,645
 158 vertebrate species (35%) in only 2.1 million km² (1.4% of the Earth's land surface). They
 159 are endangered and seem likely to lose much of their remaining primary vegetation (Myers
 160 et al., 2000).

161 In addition, Tropical Andes is in the top five hotspots with most endemic species: over
 162 20,000 plants (6.7% of all plant species in the world), and 5.7% of worldwide vertebrates.
 163 Thus, it should be considered as a hyper-hot candidate for conservation (Myers et al.,
 164 2000).

165

166 *Figure 1. Yacuambi river basin and location, coordinates and height of stations.*

167 **2.2 In situ parameters, sampling and sample pre-treatment**

168 Six stations were selected along the Yacuambi river. The stations were located close to
169 communities settlements and in straight sections of the river with little turbulence.

170 Samples were taken in four different dates (09/08/11, 22/09/11, 29/09/11, 6/10/2011).
171 These dates correspond to the dry season (López-Blanco et al., 2015; Zimmermann et al.,
172 2007), when less water flows through the rivers, gold placer mining is more intense and
173 higher concentrations of pollutants are expected. Dry season facilitates gold placer mining
174 because more sediment is above the water level and the risk of sudden floods that endanger
175 the lives of miners and machinery is reduced. Figure 1 details the location and height
176 above sea level of the stations.

177 In-situ measurements of pH, dissolved oxygen concentration, electrical conductivity, and
178 temperature were made with a Portable Multi-Parameter Meter HQ40d (Hach, United
179 States) at 20-30 cm depth. The portable device was calibrated in situ with the standards
180 provided by the manufacturer.

181 Water samples were taken in triplicate at each station following procedures described in
182 standards ISO 5667-1:2006 (Water quality. Sampling. Part 1: Guidance on the design of
183 sampling programmes and sampling techniques) and ISO 5667-3:2012 (Water quality.
184 Sampling. Part 3: Preservating and handling of water samples).

185 Three different samples were taken in each station: general parameters samples, metals and
186 pesticides samples and microbiological samples. For general parameters samples, 2 l
187 polyethylene bottles were used. This bottles were previously washed in the laboratory with
188 nonionic detergent free of metals, ammonia and phosphate, and Milli-Q water, i.e. type 1
189 water (Merck Millipore, Germany). For metals and pesticides samples 1 l topaz glass
190 bottles were used to avoid the passage of light. These bottles were previously washed in

191 the laboratory with 10% HNO₃ and Milli-Q water for metals samples and acetone and
192 hexane for pesticide samples. In the case of microbiological samples, sterilized plastic
193 vessels were used with a capacity of 300 ml with a tight lid and wide mouth. Before
194 sampling, all bottles were rinsed 3 times with the river water. When taking the sample,
195 bottles were placed in the opposite direction to the water flow.

196 Samples were placed in a portable refrigerator (4°C) in the dark and transported within 8 h
197 to Universidad Tecnica Particular de Loja's laboratories (ISO 17025 certified), where
198 chemical analyses were undertaken. Metals and pesticides samples were filtered through
199 0.45 µm pore Teflon filters. Metal samples were acidified with HNO₃ (at pH<2). All
200 samples were stored at 4°C until analysis.

201 **2.3 Laboratory analysis**

202 The parameters analyzed in the samples and the methods used are shown in Table 1. The
203 quality of the results was guaranteed thanks to the rigorous procedures followed for the
204 certification under ISO 17025, including interlaboratory tests.

205 Hereafter, the term metal includes metals and metalloids (i.e., As). Regarding metals,
206 certified standards from Merck (Germany) were employed for the preparation of 4-point
207 calibration curves. Multielemental standards and blanks were prepared and analyzed at the
208 beginning and at the end of each sequence to ensure the consistency of the dataset. Metals
209 assessed in the interlab comparisons showed differences with the average below 10%.
210 Limits of detection of metals were as follows (mg/l): Ba, 0.5; Cd, 0.01; Cr, 0.5; Pb, 0.005;
211 As, 0.005; Hg, 0.005.

212 In the case of organochlorine pesticides (α -HCH, Aldrin, 2-4 DDT and heptachlor) and
213 organophosphate pesticides (quinalphos, fonofos and malathion), the GC/MS was
214 calibrated using pesticide standards (Dr Ehrenstorfer GmbH, Germany). All the organic

215 solvents were of analytical grade (Merck, Germany) and only Milli-Q water was used. For
 216 all the analyzed compounds, relative standard deviations (RSD) were less than 15% with
 217 recovery rates ranging from 91 to 106. These values are frequent in chromatographic
 218 methods (Lambropoulou and Albanis, 2005; León et al., 2006) and therefore the accuracy
 219 is acceptable. Limits of detection of pesticides were as follows (mg/l): α -HCH, 0.077;
 220 Aldrin, 0.068; 2-4 DDT, 0.068; heptachlor, 0.056; quinalphos, 0.001; fonofos, 0.0001;
 221 malathion, 0.0001.

222 The pesticides were selected following three criteria: their lack of use in the country
 223 according to the regulations and lists (with the exception of malathion), their toxicity for
 224 people and the environment and their widespread use at some time in the past or present.

225 *Table 1. Methods of analysis of the parameters evaluated.*

Parameter	Laboratory equipment	Standard
In situ parameters		
pH	Portable Hach Multi-Parameter Meter HQ40d	ISO 10523:2012
Dissolved oxygen	..	ISO 5814:2012
Conductivity	..	ISO 7888:1985
Temperature	..	Standard Methods 2550 B
General parameter samples		
Color	Hach DR2800 spectrophotometer	ISO 7887:2011 - method C
Phosphate	..	Standard Methods 4500-P B
Nitrite	..	Standard Methods 4500-NO ₂ B
Nitrate	..	Standard Methods 4500-NO ₃ B
COD	Hach DR2800 spectrophotometer + Hach DRB 200 thermoreactor	Standard Method 5220 D
BOD ₅	Espec-Nova-400	ISO 1899-1:1998
Total solids	-	Standard Methods 2540 B
Turbidity	Hach 2100N turbidimeter	Standard Method 2130 B
Metals and pesticides samples		
Ba, Cd, Cr	Perkin–Elmer 2380 AAS	Standard Method 3111 B
Pb	Perkin–Elmer 2380 AAS + HGA 900 Graphite furnace	Standard Method 3113 B
As	Perkin–Elmer 2380 AAS + hydride generator Perkin–Elmer MSH-10	ISO 17378-2:201

Hg	''	ISO 12846:2012
Organochlorine pesticides (α -HCH, Aldrin, 2-4 DDT and heptachlor)	GC/MS Agilent 6890 gas chromatograph with a 5973 mass-selective detector	ISO 6468:1996
Organophosphate pesticides (quinalphos, fonofos and malathion)	''	EN 12918:2000
Microbiological samples		
Fecal coliforms-		Standard Methods 9222 B

226

227 **2.4 Water quality index (WQI)**

228 The National Sanitation Foundation Water Quality Index (NSFWQI, or simply WQI) was
 229 calculated to summarize in a single figure the water quality at each station based on the
 230 various parameters analyzed in this study. This index was designed by Brown et al. (1970)
 231 and improved by the National Sanitation Foundation (Lumb et al., 2011; Stambuk-
 232 Giljanovic, 1999). The use of the WQI or its variants are popular not only in USA but in
 233 many other countries (Abbasi et al., 2012; Alexakis et al., 2016; Tyagi et al., 2013).

234 To calculate the WQI, nine parameters of water quality are used (Table 2). The water
 235 quality data are transferred to a weighting curve chart, where a value of quality of the
 236 parameter i (Q_i) is obtained. Furthermore, a weight is assigned for each parameter (Table
 237 2). The mathematical expression for the WQI is as follows

238
$$WQI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Q_i W_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i}$$

239 where:

240 **Q_i (0-100):** quality of parameter i , function of value of parameter i in its original units.

241 **W_i (0-1):** weights assigned to parameter i . The sum of all W_i must be equal to 1.

242 WQI was calculated using the ICATest v1.0 software developed by Fernández et al.
243 (2001).

244 *Table 2. Parameters involved in WQI calculation and its weights (Brown et al., 1970).*

Parameter	Unit	Weight
pH		0.11
Dissolved oxygen	Saturation %	0.17
Temperature change	°C	0.10
Phosphate	PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg/l)	0.10
Nitrate	NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/l)	0.10
BOD ₅	O ₂ (mg/l)	0.11
Turbidity	NTU	0.08
Total solids	mg/l	0.07
Fecal coliforms	MPN/100 ml	0.16

245

246 WQI values allow interpreting water quality according to the classification proposed by
247 Brown et al. (1970): 0-25, very bad; 26-50, bad; 51-70, medium; 71-90, good; 91-100,
248 excellent.

249 **2.5 Statistical analysis**

250 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's post hoc test were carried out using SPSS
251 software version 20 to check the differences between parameters and indexes under
252 different circumstances, such as fecal coliforms, WQI, etc. ANOVA's output is the p
253 value, which indicates the probability that the difference between averages is due to chance
254 and not to a real difference. It is assumed that a p value lower than 0.05, expressed as
255 $p < 0.05$, reflects a significant difference and, therefore, the random explanation is
256 discarded. In case the p value is higher than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$), there is no statistical evidence
257 to reject randomness as responsible for the difference, therefore, it can not be assumed that
258 there are real differences.

259 **3 Results and discussion**

260 **3.1 Water quality index (WQI)**

261 Figure 2 shows the results of the WQI. All samples analyzed had a good (16) or medium
262 (8) water quality according to the classification proposed by Brown et al. (1970). Thus,
263 they were in the second and third best categories of quality out of five categories, as
264 mentioned in material and methods section. In the case of stations 4 and 5, all samplings
265 obtained good quality. By contrast, in station 6 all samplings showed a medium quality. In
266 the rest of the stations (1, 2 and 3) there were samplings in both categories. It is noteworthy
267 that in the second sampling, 4 stations obtained a medium quality. In contrast, 5 stations in
268 first and fourth samplings showed a good quality.

269

270 *Figure 2. Water quality index (mean ± standard deviation) classified by sampling and station.*

271 Figure 3 shows the mean of WQI at each station along the four samplings. Trends shown
272 in Figure 2 are also noticeable in Figure 3. Station 6 scored medium quality, while the rest
273 accounted for a good quality. Water quality of Yacuambi river decreased downstream from
274 station 1 to station 3 ($p < 0.05$). Station 3 represented a turning point. The average quality
275 increased in stations 4 and 5 compared to station 3. However, averages of stations 3 and 5
276 could only be stated that are different for a confidence interval of 85% ($p = 0.15$). In station
277 6, located downstream of station 5 and at the junction with the river Zamora, quality again

278 decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that the quality of Zamora river is lower
 279 and that negatively influences the final section of Yacuambi river.

280
 281 *Figure 3. Water quality index (mean ± standard deviation) classified by station.*

282 As shown in Figure 4, the averages varied across the samplings. Between sampling 1 and 2
 283 there were significant differences in the values of WQI ($p < 0.05$), in approximately 45 days.
 284 Between samplings 2 and 4 there were significant differences considering a confidence
 285 interval of 85% ($p = 0.15$). In this case, the time lapse was 14 days. However, between
 286 samplings 2 and 3 there were no significant differences ($p > 0.05$). These results
 287 demonstrate that water quality may change significantly in short periods of time.
 288 Therefore, it is recommended to carry out monitoring throughout the year at short time
 289 intervals.

290
 291 *Figure 4. Water quality index (mean ± standard deviation) classified by sampling.*

292 As explained in materials and method section, WQI calculation required assigning a
 293 quality value from 0 to 100 for each of the parameters analyzed (I_i). These quality values

294 were interpreted with the same classification used for the WQI. Fecal coliforms showed the
295 lowest quality ($p < 0.05$), with an average close to 25 (bad-very bad). Quality of coliforms
296 decreased downstream ($p < 0.05$), i.e. the coliform concentration increased towards the
297 Zamora river. The average decreased from 29.5 in station 1 (highest value) to 17.5 in
298 station 6 (lowest value). The decline was accentuated from station 4 (26.5). The values in
299 station 6 could be explained because the waters of the Yacuambi river merge with those of
300 Zamora river, which receives discharges of wastewater from the city of Loja and Zamora.

301 BOD₅ had the second lower average ($p < 0.05$), close to 57 (medium). The rest of quality
302 parameters had an average higher than 70 (good and excellent). BOD₅ reached its
303 minimum quality value at station 3 ($p < 0.05$), influenced by the discharge of wastewater
304 from the community Napurak in the La Paz canton.

305 The remaining parameters lacked a clear trend and differences were not significant. WQI
306 values for dissolved oxygen found in all the stations were higher than 90 (excellent). Such
307 high quality for dissolved oxygen favors the presence of any type of aquatic life and gives
308 a high biological potential to Yacuambi river. As shown in Figure 1, heights vary from
309 1325 masl in station 1 to 826 masl in station 6. A higher altitude is related to a location
310 closer to the source, a section of the river typically defined by steep slopes and frequent
311 water jumps, which leads to a high degree of homogenisation and oxygenation and a lower
312 organic pollution due to microbes activity.

313 Concerning the temporal variation, fecal coliforms presented values of lower quality (19)
314 in the second sampling than in the rest (27). The differences were significant with
315 sampling 3 ($p < 0.05$) and significant when considering a confidence interval of 85% with
316 the other two samplings ($p < 0.15$). All other parameters showed no significant differences
317 between samplings ($p > 0.05$). Despite these results, further research with samplings
318 distributed throughout a year is recommended to understand the temporal evolution.

319 Indexes, such as the WQI, give a general picture of the water quality at the expense of
320 losing information, since not all parameters are included, and could mask the poor state of
321 one parameter with the good state of others. Therefore, it is also necessary to discuss the
322 quality of water through individual parameters, as is done in the next section.

323 **3.2 Risk for populations and ecosystems**

324 The results were compared with water quality guidelines for the uses of these waters from
325 Ecuador and the United States (Table 3). If a parameter fails to comply with the threshold,
326 it can be concluded that the water is not suitable for that use.

327 Considering the parameters analyzed, Table 3 shows that there are more parameters
328 regulated in the Ecuadorian standards than in North Americans. In addition, Ecuadorian
329 standards impose lower limits than North Americans in most cases. Regarding
330 physicochemical parameters, Ecuadorian standards are more restrictive in 6 parameters,
331 equal in 6 and less restrictive in 2. Referring to metals, the difference is greater.
332 Ecuadorian standards are more restrictive in 10 metals, equal in 4 and less restrictive in 4.
333 In respect of pesticides, Ecuadorians standards define levels for specific pesticide and
334 groups of them, while Americans only do for each pesticide.

335 Table 3. Thresholds of analyzed parameters in standards of drinking water, preservation of aquatic
 336 life and irrigation in Ecuador (EC) and the United States (USA).

Parameter	Unit	Drinking water		Preservation of aquatic life		Irrigation water	
		EC ¹	USA ²	EC ³	USA ⁴	EC ³	USA ⁵
pH		-	-	6.5-9	6.5-9	6-9	-
Color	Pt-Co	15	-	-	-	-	-
Turbidity	NTU	5	1	-	-	-	-
Nitrate	mg/l	50	10	13	-	-	-
Nitrite	mg/l	0.2	1	0.2	-	-	-
Fecal coliforms	MPN/100 ml	0	0	-	-	1,000	-
As	mg/l	0.01	0.006	0.05	0.15	0.1	0.1
Ba	mg/l	0.7	2	1	-	-	-
Cd	mg/l	0.003	0.005	0.001	0.00072	0.05	0.01
Cr	mg/l	0.05	0.1	0.032	0.085 ⁶	0.1	0.1
Pb	mg/l	0.01	0.015	0.001	0.0025	5	5
Hg	mg/l	0.006	0.002	0.0002	0.00077	0.001	-
Organochlorine pesticides	mg/l	-	-	10	-	-	-
Organophosphate pesticides	mg/l	-	-	10	-	-	-

337 ¹ Ecuadorian quality standard for drinking water (NTE INEN 1 108:2011) (Ecuadorian
 338 Institute of Standardization, 2011).

339 ² Table of Regulated Drinking Water Contaminants in the EPA's National Primary
 340 Drinking Water Regulations (NPDWR) (United States Environmental Protection Agency,
 341 2015).

342 ³ Acuerdo Ministerial 28, de 13 de febrero de 2015, por el que se reforma el Texto
 343 Unificado de Legislación Ambiental Secundaria del Ministerio del Ambiente (TULSMA)
 344 (Ecuadorian Ministry of the Environment, 2015).

345 ⁴ Levels of chronic exposure for freshwaters registered in EPA's National Recommended
 346 Water Quality Criteria - Aquatic Life Criteria Table (United States Environmental
 347 Protection Agency, 2016).

348 ⁵ Recommended limits for constituents in reclaimed water for irrigation in long term use.
 349 EPA's Guidelines for water reuse (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 1992).

350 ⁶ This level of Cr is calculated as the sum of Cr (III) and Cr (VI) given in the original table.
 351

352 None of the samples could be considered potable according to Ecuadorian and North
 353 American drinking water standards (Table 3 and Figure 5). All samples exceeded the
 354 thresholds of fecal coliforms and As of both standards, color (only Ecuadorian standard)
 355 and turbidity (only North American standard). 42% of the analyzed samples exceeded the
 356 Ecuadorian threshold for Pb, specifically all samples in station 1 and some in the stations

357 2, 3 and 4. Differences between samplings were appreciable. 67% samples of third
358 sampling exceeded the Pb threshold, while only 18% of the second sampling. Most of
359 those samples complied with North American standards. Regarding turbidity, 58% of the
360 samples surpassed Ecuadorian threshold (5 NTU), i.e. all of the samples in stations 2, 4
361 and 6 and 50% of the samples of station 1.

362 Arsenic displayed a similar trend in all samplings. Station 1 showed the lowest
363 concentration of As, followed by a significant increase on station 2 ($p < 0.05$), where the
364 highest concentrations are found. Station 2 represented a turning point and concentrations
365 in stations 3 and 4 were lower again.

366 None of the samples were suitable to preserve aquatic life according to Ecuadorian
367 standards and only station 5 in the sampling 1 is adequate according to North American
368 standards (Table 3). The thresholds for Pb was exceeded in all samples (with the exception
369 of station 5, sampling 1 for North American standard). The Ecuadorian threshold for As
370 was exceeded at all stations in samplings 2, 3 and 4 (75% of samples). But at none of them
371 in the North American standard due to higher threshold. The pH was lower than 6.5 in 75%
372 of samples of station 1 and contravene both standards.

373 Half of the samples were not suitable to irrigate according to Ecuadorian standards (Table
374 3). Unsuitable samples were concentrated in stations 6 (100%) and 3 (75%). Fecal
375 coliforms exceeded the threshold of 1,000 MPN/100 ml in all samples of sampling 2 and
376 station 6. Arsenic also exceeded the threshold for Ecuador and North America (0.1 mg/l) in
377 21% of samples. Specifically, 75% of station 3 and 25% of stations 4 and 5.

378 The concentrations of the rest of the metals studied were below detection limits in all
379 samples: Ba (<0.5 mg/l), Cd (<0.01 mg/l), Cr (<0.5 mg/l) and Hg (<0.005 mg/l), which can
380 be considered low.

381 The concentrations of organochlorine and organophosphate pesticides in all samples tested
 382 were below the limit of detection (α -HCH: 0.077; Aldrin: 0.068; 2-4 DDT: 0.068;
 383 heptachlor: 0.056; quinalphos: 0.001; fonofos: 0.0001; malathion: 0.0001). These data can
 384 be considered low and meet with Ecuadorian standards described above (Table 3).

385

386 *Figure 5. Number of times the thresholds of the drinking water (D), preservation of aquatic life (P)*
 387 *and irrigation (I) regulations are exceeded at each station in the 4 samplings. In brackets, the*
 388 *number of times thresholds are exceeded in a station or for a particular parameter.*

389 Figure 5 describes that the thresholds of As, Pb and fecal coliforms for drinking,
 390 preservation of aquatic life and irrigation are those exceeded more times.

391 **3.3 Potential sources of pollution**

392 Several threats could affect water quality. Gold placer mining can cause several impacts on
 393 water, such as turbidity by resuspension of sediment. Turbidity values found (below 20
 394 NTU) are sufficient to exceed the North American standard threshold (United States
 395 Environmental Protection Agency, 2015). However, this result suggests that mining had a
 396 low influence on turbidity. The large flow of Yacuambi river requires a significant amount
 397 of particulate material with a high proportion of fine sediment to affects turbidity
 398 significantly over long distances. During sampling, it was noted that turbidity of the water
 399 increased in some gold placer mining sites. However, turbidity decreased a few meters

400 downstream due to the return of the material to the riverbed. This is confirmed by the data
401 found in Mongolia, where the Tuul river turbidity reached up to 700 NTU due to effluents
402 of gold placer mining (Batsaikhan et al., 2016).

403 Concentrations of Hg below 5 µg/l in all water samples can be considered low. These
404 results suggest that the amalgamation of gold with Hg in Yacuambi is not intensive,
405 probably because gold nuggets has a large size and high purity. It could also be explained
406 due to the application of measures to prevent spills with high Hg content and Hg emissions
407 into the atmosphere. These data are in agreement with those of López-Blanco et al. (2015),
408 who found that Hg levels in soils along the Yacuambi river (below 0.5 mg/kg) are far
409 below the Quality Guidelines for the Protection of Environmental and Human Health set
410 on 6.6 mg/kg (Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment, 2007). The levels of Hg
411 in water are in agreement with those of the Nangaritza River, also affected by gold mining,
412 where the concentration is below 1 µg/l (González-Merizalde et al., 2016).

413 However, López-Blanco et al. (2015) found that Hg concentrations in soils of the
414 Yacuambi's river bank grow downstream, reaching higher values in the surroundings of
415 the mouth than at the headwaters, free from the influence of mining. The absence of other
416 potential sources of Hg in the Yacuambi basin suggests that gold placer mining is the main
417 source of this slight increase. Furthermore, although concentrations of Hg in water are
418 below drinking water thresholds, there may be a risk for humans since Hg is also present in
419 the air. In a nearby area, the Nangaritza River Basin, concentrations of Hg in water were
420 reported below 1 µg/l. However, Hg concentrations in children's urine were found above
421 international guidelines (20 µg/g creatinine) for the production of adverse health effects
422 (González-Merizalde et al., 2016).

423 What is more, considering the use of Hg in mining was banned in Ecuador in 2013
424 (Ecuadorian National Assembly, 2013), more control by the local authorities is needed to

425 ensure the enforcement of the law. Further research on the risk of Hg in humans is
426 recommended through the study of Hg in urine.

427 Arsenic values in Yacuambi river are higher than those (0.0002-0.0159 mg/l) found in the
428 river Congüime, near the Yacuambi (León-Carrasco, 2014) although significant
429 anthropogenic sources (artisanal scale gold mining and placer gold mining) take place in
430 the Congüime river. The artisanal scale gold mining exploits a vein with arsenopyrite,
431 which is accumulated in the streams, accelerating the chemical oxidation and release of As
432 (León-Carrasco, 2014). Thorslund et al. (2016) found in Lake Baikal, Russia, exposed to
433 gold placer mining, concentrations of up to 0.015 mg/l of As in water, whereas in
434 Yacuambi were found concentrations up to almost 10 times that (0.135 mg/l) and
435 concentrations of 0.09 mg/l were common. These results suggest that natural and
436 anthropogenic sources, such as gold placer mining, could act combined to explain the
437 concentrations of As observed in Yacuambi.

438 The sediment movement carried out by mining exposes deep sediments, predictably under
439 anaerobic conditions, to aerobic conditions in which As has a tendency to solubilize (Bradl
440 et al., 2005). According to López-Blanco et al. (2015), As concentrations in soils of the
441 banks of the Yacuambi river are highly concentrated (over 30 mg/kg). Six of the seven
442 samples exceeded the Quality Guidelines for the Protection of Environmental and Human
443 Health set on 12 mg/kg (Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment, 2007), in one
444 case, more than 10 times. Thus, high concentrations of As could also occur in the sediment
445 and this could lead to the high levels in water (Sanyal and Nasar, 2002). Under reducing
446 conditions, As may be sequestered by co-precipitation with sulphide minerals (Brammer
447 and Ravenscroft, 2009; Kumar et al., 2016; Sun et al., 2016).

448 Further research is needed to measure the concentration of As in the sediment and to
449 characterize whether the As belongs mainly to the labile fractions that would facilitate its
450 release.

451 In Yacuambi river, up to 0.113 mg/l of Pb in water have been found, and values of 0.005 to
452 0.010 mg/l are common. Thorslund et al. (2016) found in Lake Baikal, Russia, exposed to
453 gold placer mining, Pb concentrations up to 0.006 mg/l in water and the most common
454 values were between 0.001 and 0.0015 mg/l. Concentrations of Pb in the sediments of the
455 Yacuambi river banks are lower compared to those of As (López-Blanco et al., 2015).
456 Only one of the samples of López-Blanco et al. (2015) exceeded 30 mg/kg and none
457 exceeded the values of the Quality Guidelines for the Protection of Environmental and
458 Human Health set on 70 mg/kg (Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment, 2007).
459 Gold placer mining could lead to high Pb concentrations in water, but lower concentrations
460 in soil helps to explain that the Pb concentrations in water are lower than those of As.
461 Considering both elements have the same maximum value allowed in drinking water, the
462 Pb exceeds the limit on fewer occasions.

463 Fecal coliforms can be considered high, reaching up to 8,200 MPN/100 ml, and values
464 above 500 MPN/100 ml were common. These levels exceeded in several times those of a
465 river near the area, the Congüime river, below 330 MPN/100 ml (León-Carrasco, 2014).
466 Several reasons are possible, mainly urban wastewater discharges from untreated
467 watershed populations, but also effluents of aquaculture of Tilapia, manure from livestock
468 and cows that access the river to drink.

469 The results found in this study indicate a non-intensive use of organochlorine and
470 organophosphorus pesticides in Yacuambi catchment. In fact, all pesticides were below the
471 limit of detection. Many farmers only fumigate 1 or 3 times a year. In addition, many
472 farmers use non-water soluble pesticides that would tend to be attached to soils and

473 sediments. Further research is needed to confirm whether water-insoluble pesticides
474 potentially used in agriculture are present in sediments, e.g. those belonging to the
475 sulfonylurea group.

476 **4 Conclusions**

477 The waters of the Yacuambi river have a good and medium quality according to the
478 classification of Water Quality Index (WQI) proposed by Brown et al. (1970). I.e., they are
479 in the second and third best quality category out of five.

480 According to WQI, water quality is variable along the Yacuambi river. Water quality
481 decreases from downstream of the head to the middle section, where it starts to increase
482 again but then becomes significantly lower at the mouth. This fact suggests that the
483 Zamora river negatively influences the Yacuambi river. Fecal coliforms and BOD₅ are the
484 parameters with the lowest quality. All other parameters have an average quality
485 corresponding to good and excellent categories.

486 Yacuambi river waters are unsuitable for human consumption and preservation of aquatic
487 life according to the Ecuadorian and North American standards. For human consumption,
488 color, As and fecal coliforms fail to comply with the standards in most cases. For
489 preservation of aquatic life, the threshold for Pb is exceeded in all samples.

490 Yacuambi river waters are not always suitable for irrigation, especially in the end and
491 medium sections. Arsenic and fecal coliforms exceeded the limits required by the standard
492 for this use.

493 Further research is required on the river Yacuambi to identify and control sources of
494 pollution in the basin and to ensure water quality for populations and ecosystems.

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